

Condensation of *o*-Aminonitriles and Acetic Acid : A Simple Procedure for the Formation of Condensed Pyrimidines

AMRIK SINGH* and AVTAR SINGH UPPAL

Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University,
Amritsar-143 005 (India)

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O-Acetylaminothiazolines(II) obtained by the acetylation of *o*-aminonitriles yield condensed pyrimidines(III) quite readily under different conditions¹⁻⁵. We have found that 4-amino-3-aryl-5-carbonitrile/carboxamido-2-imino-4-thiazolines(IV, R=CN, CONH₂) with acetic anhydride give 2-acetylmino-3-aryl-5-carboxamido/carbonitrile-2-imino-4-thiazolines(V, R=CONH₂, CN)⁶ and not 4-acetylamino-3-aryl-5-carboxamido/carbonitrile-2-imino-4-thiazolines(X, R=CONH₂, CN)⁷. However, these thiazolines(V) when heated in polyphosphoric acid at 140-150° furnish 3-aryl-2-imino-5-methylthiazolo(4,5-d)pyrimidin-7-ones(VI) as major products; in addition three other minor products (VII-IX) were obtained⁶. The product (VI) seemed to have resulted from the split of acetyl group from 2-imino nitrogen in (V) followed by its recombination at 4-amino group and cyclisation. Part of the deacetylated product undergoes hydrolysis of the amino and nitrile groups alongwith migration of the aryl group from position 3 to position 2 to yield (VIII) and a portion of (VIII) further gives (IX) on hydrolysis of the amide group followed by decarboxylation of the resulting carboxylic acid. The product (VII) has either resulted from further acetylation of (VI) or from the acetylation of (V) followed by cyclisation. It may be pointed out that thiazolo(4,5-d)pyrimidin-7-ones(VI) have been found to be a new class of CNS depressants⁶.

In order to save one step in the formation of (VI) it was considered worthwhile to attempt its preparation directly from 4-amino-3-aryl-5-carbonitrile/carboxamido-4-thiazolines(IV, R=CN,

CONH₂) and acetic acid in the presence of polyphosphoric acid. It was found that both types of thiazolines(IV, R=CN, CONH₂) when heated with acetic acid or acetic anhydride in the presence of polyphosphoric acid at 140-150° furnished the desired thiazolo(4,5-d)pyrimidines(VI) in very good yields (70%). The products obtained in this procedure were much more pure than those obtained previously. Evidently the reaction proceeded through prior acetylation at 4-amino followed by cyclisation of the resulting 4-acetylaminothiazolines. The fact that acetylation occurs at 2-imino group under usual acetylation conditions and at 4-amino group under strongly acidic conditions can be readily accounted on the basis of greater nucleophilic and basic character of 2-imino nitrogen as compared with 4-amino nitrogen. When the conditions are not strongly acidic, it is at 2-imino group where the acetylation occurs. Under strongly acidic conditions the protonation also occurs at 2-imino group as a result its nucleophilic character is decreased. On the other hand, nucleophilic character of 4-amino nitrogen atom is relatively unaffected under these conditions. Furthermore acetic anhydride or acetic acid might be present as some reactive species and hence it is the 4-amino group where the acetylation occurs under strongly acidic conditions.

In order to test the applicability of the above mentioned procedure for making other condensed pyrimidines, *o*-aminobenzonitrile was condensed with acetic acid in the presence of polyphosphoric acid when 2-methylquinazolin-4-one was obtained in 50% yield.

Formation of 2-imino-3-aryl-5-methylthiazolo(4,5-d)pyrimidin-7-one (VI) :

2-Imino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-carbonitrile/carboxamido-4-thiazoline(IV, R=CN, CONH₂) (1 g) was taken up in polyphosphoric acid (4 g) and acetic acid (0.25 ml) or acetic anhydride (0.15 ml) was added, the contents were heated at 140-150° for 30 minutes. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water (30 ml) and the excess acid was neutralised initially with ammonia and last traces of the acid was neutralised with aq. sodium carbonate as the product is soluble in excess of mineral alkalis. The product (VI) was separated out, washed with water and purified by dissolving in aq. ammonia, reprecipitation was done with dil. acetic acid. The products obtained were identical to those already reported⁶. The following derivatives of (VI) were obtained through this procedure: Ar=phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl.

Formation of 2-methylquinazolin-4-one(XII) :

o-Aminobenzonitrile(XI; 2 g) was heated in polyphosphoric acid (6 g) alongwith acetic acid (1.1 ml) at 140-150° for two hours. The reaction

mixture on dilution with water (50 ml) gave 2-methylquinazolin-4-one. The product after purification was found to be identical to that reported in literature (mmp, tlc)¹.

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Chemical Examination of *Cassia javanica* Flowers

J. SINGH, A. R. TIWARI and R. D. TIWARI

Chemical Laboratories, Allahabad University, Allahabad-211 002

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IN an earlier communication¹ isolation and structural studies of flavonoids from the flowers of this plant had been reported.

We report in this communication isolation of three aliphatic alcohols (ceryl alcohol, octacosanol and hentriacontanol), β -sitosterol and a new anthocyanin (peonidin-3-O- α -L (-) rhamnopyranoside) from the flowers of *Cassia javanica* Linn.

Alcoholic extract of the flowers of *Cassia javanica* was hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide and the unsaponifiable material extracted with benzene and chromatographed over alumina column and eluted with different solvent mixtures according to their polarity. Petroleum ether : benzene (4 : 1) fraction yielded β -sitosterol, petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) fraction yielded ceryl alcohol, benzene (100%) yielded octacosanol and benzene : ethyl acetate (9 : 1) fraction yielded hentriacontanol.

These compounds were identified by mp, mmp, derivatisation and I.R., nmr spectra and mass fragmentation pattern.

The fresh flowers of *Cassia javanica* were extracted with ethanolic hydrochloric acid at room temperature. The extract was concentrated at reduced pressure and kept at room temperature and the residue thus obtained was crystallised from amyl alcohol hydrochloric acid mixture. It gave positive Molisch test and other reactions characteristic of anthocyanins. On hydrolysis with 20% hydrochloric acid it gave rhamnose (PC, Osazone) and an aglycone, anthocyanidin which gave specific colour reactions of peonidin derivatives and had λ_{\max} at 542 nm in ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution.

On permanganate oxidation the anthocyanidin gave vanillic acid as one of the oxidation products, which fixed the methoxyl group at position-3' and a hydroxyl group at position-4' in ring B. On alkali degradation the aglycone gave phloroglucinol and vanillic acid. Thus there are hydroxyl groups at position-5, 7 and 4' and a methoxyl group at position-3'. Thus the aglycone is peonidin. Finally, the anthocyanidin was confirmed as peonidin by co-chromatography on paper using Forestal solvent with an authentic sample of peonidin isolated from fresh *Viola tricolor* flowers.

The anthocyanin and anthocyanidin had λ_{\max} at 532 nm and 542 nm respectively in ethanolic hydrochloric acid solution. A hypsochromic shift of 10 nm in the glycoside indicated the attachment of rhamnose in position-3 of peonidin². That rhamnose in the glycoside is in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation when it consumed 2 moles of periodate per mole of the glycoside and produced 1 mole of formic acid. The glycoside hydrolysed by takadiastase thereby showing the presence of α -linkage. On the basis of these results the glycoside was identified as peonidin-3-O- α -L(-)rhamnopyranoside.

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